

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B042
Date: 24 Aug 2004
Take Off 13:13:53
Landing: 15:19:27
Flight Time 2h05m34

Trials Instructions: ADRIEX – transit to Treviso with all instruments operated.

Operating Area: Cranfield to Treviso via airways as required.

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
4	Dropsondes	Steve Devereau	FAAM
5	Core Chemistry	Ken Dewey	FAAM
6	CVI	Paul James	FAAM
7	CCN	Stuart Heath	FAAM
8	ARIES	Alan Vance	Met Office
9	SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
10	AMS	Jonny Crosier	UMIST
11	VACC	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University
12	Passenger	Peter Chappell	Directflight Ops
13	Passenger	Ben Tobin	Directflight Ops
14	Passenger	Martin Darling	Avalon
15	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
16			
17			
18			
19			

Flight Track:

B042 Track 24-AUG-04

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B042

Date: 24-AUG-2004

Project: ADRIEX

Location: Transit Cranfield to Treviso

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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131353		T/O	2.1 kft	223	From Cranfield
150116		AVM	23.3 kft	178	Top of descent
151927		Land	-.01 kft	069	At Treviso

B042 Track 24-AUG-04

FAAM Sortie Brief

ADRIEX Transit flight

Flight No: B042

Date 24 August 2004

Trial Objectives:

Transit to Treviso with all instruments operated.

Location:

Cranfield to Treviso via airways as required.

Weather:

No weather dependence for instrument operation.

1. Flight Pattern:

2. Take off from Cranfield airport at 1300GMT.

3. Transit to Treviso as flight plan ~~230KIAS~~ FL 250 → FL 270

4. Operate instruments as required for in flight testing .

5. Land Treviso.

Ken Dewey

24 11

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B043

Date: 27/8/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
08:	Ch1-Ch3	Noise	Too Noisy								Start Profile 1
08:03:07	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			2						FL070
08:04:20	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			2						FL080
08:05:20	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									FL090
08:06:12	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									FL100 PCASP Heaters ON
08:07:15	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			2						FL110
08:	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									FL120
08:	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									FL140
08:14:10	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									End of Profile 1 @ FL150
08:19:47	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									Start Profile 2 from FL150
08:21:30	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			1						FL140
08:22:14	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			1						FL130
08:25:04	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			1						FL100
08:26:06	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			1						FL090
08:29:20	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			1						FL080
08:33:41	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									End of Profile 2 @ 3000'
08:35:00	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									Start Run 1.1 @ 3000'
08:36:00	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			10						
08:38:00	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			8						
08:40:00	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			5						
08:42:00	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			8						
08:44:00	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			8						
08:46:00	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			5						
08:48:07	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									End of Run 1.1
08:49:13	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									Start Run 1.2 @ 3000'
08:50:00	100				5						
08:52:00	80				5						
08:54:00	80				5						
08:56:00	50				5						
08:58:00	50				5						
09:00:00	50				5						PCASP heaters ON
09:02:00	150				10						

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B043

Date: 27/8/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
09:04:00	150			10							
09:05:09											End of Run
09:06:26											Start Run 1.3 @ 3000'
09:07:00	100			10							
09:09:00	100			8							
09:11:00	150			8							
09:13:00	150			8							
09:15:00	200			10							
09:17:00	100			5							
09:19:25											End of Run 1.3
09:20:35											Start Run 1.4 @ 3000'
09:21:00	500			10							
09:23:00	500			12							
09:25:00	300			12							
09:27:00	300			12							
09:29:00	300			10							
09:31:00	30			2							
09:33:00	30			2							
09:34:15											End of Run 1.4
09:38:35											Start P3 from FL030
09:39:47	20			1							FL040
09:40:43	10			1							FL050
09:41:48	10										FL060
09:44:50	5										FL090
09:45:55	5										FL100
09:46:50	5										FL110
09:49:30	3										FL120
09:50:20											End of P3 @ FL150
09:55:49											Start Profile 4 from FL150
09:57:09	1										FL140
09:58:25	20			1							FL130
09:59:30	20			1							FL120 PCASP Heaters OFF

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B

Date:

Operator:

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:00:27											FL110
10:01:30											FL100
10:03:25											FL080
10:04:30											FL070
10:05:28											FL060
10:06:30											FL050
10:07:30											FL040
10:08:35											End of Profile 4 @ FL030
10:13:32											Start Run 2.1 @ FL030
10:14:00											
10:16:00											
10:18:00											
10:20:00											
10:22:00											
10:24:00											
10:26:00											
10:28:00											
10:30:00											
10:30:38											End of Run 2.1
10:32:04											Start Run 2.1 @ FL030
10:33:00											
10:35:00											
10:37:00											
10:39:00											
10:41:00											
10:43:00											
10:45:00											
10:45:37											End of Run 2.1
10:46:52											Start Profile 5 From FL030
10:48:32											
10:											
10:											

SWS/SHIMS PRE-FLIGHT LOG		Date	24/8/04	Flight	B 042
Operator(s)	A. WILSON		Campaign	ADRIEX	
Departure	24 0131400 Z		Arrival	24 151930	

Physical system setup

Module Number Serial	Connection(e.g.SWS nir, SHIMS upper)
0 00308 003803 5724	SWS NIR
27581	SWS VIS

System functionality check After system stabilizes

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0 secs.	at time	132000 Z
Freezer temp	-7°C			

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

 Flight No. **B. 042**

 Date **24.8.04**

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU			<u>Probes</u>		
GPS		✓	FFSSP		✓
Satcom C			PCASP		
Satcom H		✓	2D-P	✗	
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	✗	
De-Iced Temp			Cloudscope	✗	
Non De-Iced		✓	SID 1		✓
Heimann		✓	SID 2	✗	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CPI	✗	
G. Eastern			HVPS	✗	
J. Williams		✓	<u>Racks:</u>		
Nevzorov	✗		INC	✗	
TWC	✗		CCN / CNC		✓
FWVS		✓	CVI		✓
<u>Radiometers</u>					
Upper Clear			<u>Aerosol</u>		
“ Red		✓	PSAP		
“ Silicon		✓	Nephelometer		✓
“ JO1D		✓	AMS		✓
Lower Clear					
“ Red		✓			
“ Silicon		✓			
“ JO1D		✓			
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	✗				
MARSS	✗				
DEIMOS	✗				
ARIES		✓			
SWS / SHM		✓			
<u>Chemistry</u>					
Ozone		✓			
ECGC					
NOX		✓			
CO		✓	<u>Others:</u>		
ORAC	✗				
PAN					
PERCA	✗				
WAS		✓			